

PRODUCTION OF THE JOSHI EFFECT IN OXYGEN UNDER SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE. PART V. INFLUENCE OF THE FREQUENCY OF THE EXCITING POTENTIAL

BY S. R. MOHANTY

Influence of the frequency f of the exciting potential on the Joshi effect Δi in oxygen, enclosed in a Siemens' tube at 331 mm. (32°) Hg pressure, has been investigated. Both the 'threshold' potential V_m and Δi decrease, the former from 2.7 to 0.7 kV (r. m. s.) and the latter from 42 to 21 % (current i in dark, $i^0 = 3$), with f increased from 50 to 500 μ . Δi is negligibly small below V_m . It is absent in high frequency (3-11 Mc) conduction at low potentials. Since the proportion of dielectric in i increases with f , and conduction mainly dielectric below V_m and with high frequencies at low potentials, the above results do not support Parshad's view that Δi represents a diminution of the dielectric as distinct from conduction current. Diminution of wattage dissipated in the ozoniser on irradiation corresponding to Δi indicates on the other hand that Δi results chiefly from suppression of conduction current. Change under light of dielectric conductivity can, at best, be a minor explanation.

It has already been shown (Part I, Mohanty and Kamath, this *Journal*, 1948, 26, 405; Mohanty, Part VI, *ibid.*, communicated) that the magnitude of the Joshi effect Δi in oxygen is dependent upon the applied (alternating) potential V . That the frequency f of this last is another important determinant, was revealed by the preliminary investigations of the author (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1949, Part III, *Chem. Sec.*, Abst. No. 25). It was of interest therefore to study this in some detail.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Single phase alternating currents of 50 and 500 cycles frequency were obtained from rotary convertors worked off 220 volts, D. C. mains. A Hartley type oscillator was used for generating high frequencies.

The general experimental arrangement and the circuit employed are shown in Fig. 1. The oscillator consisted chiefly of a 6L6 pentode (RCA), 20,000 Ω grid resistance, 0.00025 μ F tuning condenser and tuning inductance. A variable 0.0001 μ F capacitance was included in series with the receiving coil; this served to tune the receiving circuit to the frequencies generated by the oscillator. The frequency f was varied by altering the dial-position, and hence the capacitance of the tuning condenser. From calibrations made with a wavemeter,

the various dial-positions corresponded to the frequency range of 3-11 megacycles per second.

A Siemens' tube filled with purified oxygen at 331 mm. pressure (32°) served the discharge vessel. The current was observed with a reflection galvanometer actuated by a Cambridge vacuo-junction V. J. (Fig. 1). The source of light consist

of a battery of two 200 watt incandescent (glass) bulbs run at 200 volts, and placed at a distance of 20 cm. from the discharge tube. The mode of observation of Δi was similar to that described in Part I (Mohanty and Kamath, *loc. cit.*).

Three series of observations were made : (i) when the discharge tube was excited at different V varied in the range of 2.6 kV (r. m. s.) of 50 cycles frequency, (ii) with 0.5-1 kV of 500 cycles frequency, and (iii) when the system was fed with high frequencies in the aforementioned range. The potential developed across the ozoniser in (iii) was kept constant ; it was, as determined with a thermionic tube voltmeter, 1.17 volts. The relevant circuit for (i) and (ii) is represented by α , and that for (iii) by β (Fig. 1). The current in dark i_0 , that under irradiation i_L , the net Joshi effect Δi and the relative effect $\% \Delta i$ for different V and f are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Influence of the frequency of exciting potential on the Joshi effect in oxygen.

$pO_2 = 331$ mm. (32°).

Temp. = 20° .

Detector = Vacuo-junction.

Source of radiations = Two 200 volt-200 watt (glass) bulbs, 20 cm. from the ozoniser.

V (kV, r. m. s.)	i_0	i_L	Δi	$\% \Delta i$
50 ω ; $V_m = 2.7$ kV (r. m. s.)				
2.6	1	1	—	—
2.67	2.55	3.47	1.14	44.7
2.93	5.48	3.46	2.02	36.9
3.2	7.62	5.2	2.42	31.8
3.47	8.94	6.65	2.38	26.6
3.73	10.10	7.55	2.55	25.2
4	11.14	8.49	2.65	23.8
4.27	12.13	9.27	2.86	23.6
4.53	13.15	10.20	2.95	22.4
4.8	14.21	11.09	3.12	22
5.07	15.30	11.96	3.34	21.8
5.33	16.25	13.00	3.25	20.0
500 ω ; $V_m = 0.7$ kV (r. m. s.)				
0.67	—	—	—	—
0.69	2.65	2.12	0.53	20.0
0.72	4.69	3.74	0.95	20.3
0.75	7.55	6.00	1.55	20.5
0.77	10.20	8.49	1.71	16.8
0.8	12.84	10.73	2.11	16.4
0.83	16.19	13.93	2.26	14
0.85	20.04	17.41	2.63	13.1
3—11 M_{ω} .				
Dial position of condenser.	Approx. f in M_{ω} .			
0	3.4	9.5	9.5	—
30	3.7	7.6	7.6	—
60	4.0	15.6	15.6	—
90	4.5	15	15	—
120	5.3	10.6	10.6	—
150	6.7	10.7	10.7	—
180	10.6	12.4	12.4	—

DISCUSSION

It has been shown by Joshi (*Curr. Sci.*, 1939, 8, 548) that measurements of the minimum 'threshold' potential V_m , at which i increases rapidly with the applied V , are markedly sensitive to changes in f . That V_m would appear to be more sensitive to such changes than the Paschen potential has also been emphasized by him (Joshi, *ibid.*, 1946, 15, 281). In agreement with the above, it is observed that whereas V_m for 50 cycles is about 2.7 kV, it is as small as 0.7 kV, under otherwise identical conditions, with 500 cycles (cf. Table I). Further, increase of i with V is far more rapid in the latter than in the former case. Thus e.g., increase of $V_{f=50}$ from 2.67 to 5.33 kV increases i_b from 2.55 to 16.25 units, i.e., by about 6 times; the corresponding i_s increases by about 9 times, from 1.41 to 13.00. On the other hand, increase of $V_{f=500}$ over a comparatively small range, viz., from 0.69 to 0.85 kV, increases i_b from 2.65 to 20.04 i.e., by about 7 times; i_s increases by about 8 times, from 2.12 to 17.41, over the same potential range.

In agreement with the general result due to Joshi (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, A22, 389), and the earlier observation of the author and Kamath (*loc. cit.*) in the gas, it is found that the effect is not observed below V_m . Further, $\% \Delta i$ is maximum near this potential; it is 44.7 with 50 cycles, and 20.0 with 500 cycles. These results bring out the fundamental significance of V_m in relation to the Joshi effect phenomenon.

Since the exciting potentials were, of necessity, different in the two cases, it is not possible to compare Δi or $\% \Delta i$ at 50 and 500 cycles under conditions of constant V . Comparisons are therefore made under conditions of constant i_b . For this purpose, values for Δi at the above two frequencies are plotted against the corresponding values of i_b (Fig. 2). It will be seen that the curve for 500 cycles is well below that for 50 cycles, indicating that under constant i_b conditions, Δi for 50 cycles is larger than that for 500 cycles. This supports the general validity of Joshi's observation (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, A22, 389) that *ceteris paribus* $\% \Delta i$ decreases as the input frequency (i.e., of the A. C. supply) is increased.

Results in Table I reveal further that the system excited with high frequencies in the range 3-11 megacycles does not show the effect. The observations of Joshi and Lad (*ibid.*, 1945, A22, 293), Tiwari and Prasad (*Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 229), Lahiry and Das-Gupta (*Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1949, Part III, Phys. Sec., Abst. No. 30), and Das-Gupta (*Science & Culture*, 1945-46, 11, 318) with chlorine were similar. The chief determinant of the Joshi effect phenomenon is a large enough field to produce ionisa-

FIG. 2

tion by collision of the gas in the annular space. The *effect* is absent under high frequency conduction, since under such conditions the corresponding electric field is so low that the system functions as a capacity only.

Parshad (*Nature*, 1945, 155, 362) has envisaged the mechanism of the Joshi effect from the standpoint of Kramers' quantum mechanical theory of light dispersion. He considers that consequent on irradiation, the gas is excited to higher vibrational and electronic states. For these, due to operations of negative terms in Kramers' dispersion formula, the refractive index n should be less than that of the normal gas. It follows from this, and the well-known relation due to Maxwell, viz., $n^2 = \epsilon$ (where ϵ is the dielectric constant) that ϵ should diminish. Since this last is a measure of the electrostatic capacity of the system, Parshad concludes that the Joshi effect represents a diminution of the displacement, as distinct from conduction or ohmic, current. Since ionisation and excitation are different stages in the same direction, the smaller dielectric constant of ionised as compared with unionised gases constitutes, according to him, an indirect experimental confirmation of the above interpretation. The results of the present experiments, however, do not support Parshad's view. Thus, whereas Δi decreases with f , the proportion of the dielectric current is known to increase. Further, Δi is negligibly small below V_m (at which ionisation by collision commences in the annular space), and does not occur with high frequencies at low potentials; conduction in both these cases is mainly capacitative. From the observation that the wattage dissipated in the ozoniser decreases on irradiation corresponding to Δi , Joshi (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, A22, 225) concludes that the *effect* Δi results chiefly from a reduction of the conduction or ohmic part of i . Further, he observes, "that the corresponding displacement current may also be affected is suggested by a frequent observation of a sensible movement and distortion on irradiation of the steadied wave-form on the oscillograph, due perhaps to a frequency or/and phase shift; by the observed influence on % Δi of capacitative changes in the system, suggesting a change under light of the dielectric constant of the ionised gas as a possibly partial, though at best a minor explanation of this phenomenon of ageing, adsorption and the nature of the wall material".

Grateful thanks of the author are due to Professor S. S. Joshi for having suggested the problem and for his keen interest in the work, and to Mr. P. L. Sarma for having kindly constructed the H. F. generator.